

Annexe 2: An Examination of Methodological Approaches in Applied Technology Classrooms: A Reflective Perspective from Vocational and Training Educators

Fundamental coding scheme considered for enhancing rigour in thematic analysis. (Soratto et al., 2020)

Clear Research Design	Define Research Questions and Objectives:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clearly articulate the research questions and objectives to guide the analysis. Ensure that the thematic analysis aligns with the overall research design and goals.
Data Management	Use Qualitative Data Analysis Software	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employ software tools (ATLAS.ti) for efficient data management, coding, and retrieval. Organize data systematically with clear labels and metadata.
Coding Consistency	Develop a Coding Framework:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create a preliminary coding framework based on initial readings of the data. Ensure that codes are clearly defined and understood by all researchers involved.
	Iterative Coding Process	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage in multiple rounds of coding to refine and consolidate codes. Use a combination of open coding (initial) and axial coding (refining and linking codes).
Collaborative Analysis	Involve Multiple Researchers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Work with a team of researchers to enhance the reliability and depth of coding. Regularly discuss coding decisions and emerging themes to ensure consistency.
	Inter-Coder Reliability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Calculate inter-coder reliability to measure the level of agreement between different coders. Resolve discrepancies through discussions and consensus.
Thorough Documentation	Maintain an Audit Trail	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Document every step of the analysis process, including coding decisions, theme development, and changes made. Keep reflective notes and memos to capture thoughts, insights, and rationales behind coding choices.
Data Saturation	Ensure Data Saturation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continue coding and analyzing data until no new themes emerge, indicating data saturation. Verify that the themes comprehensively represent the data set.
Theme Validation	Triangulation:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use multiple data sources or methods to validate themes. Cross-check findings with existing literature, other researchers, or additional data.
	Member Checking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> If feasible, seek feedback from participants to validate the themes and interpretations. Incorporate participants' perspectives to enhance credibility.
Reflexivity	Reflect on Researcher Bias	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acknowledge and reflect on potential biases and their impact on the analysis. Engage in reflexive practices, such as keeping a reflexive journal, to critically examine assumptions and decisions.
Rich, Thick Descriptions	Provide Detailed Context:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Offer rich, thick descriptions of the data, themes, and contexts to enhance transferability. Use illustrative quotes and examples to support themes and interpretations.
Transparent Reporting	Comprehensive Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clearly describe the methodology, including data collection, coding process, theme development, and validation techniques. Ensure that the report is transparent and provides sufficient detail for others to understand and evaluate the analysis.